

EBFMC25-OOP-07 · The Impact of Vaccination Status on Infectious Disease Clinics: The Case of COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The aim of this study is to investigate whether vaccination, which is the most significant preventive measure against infectious diseases, has a contribution to prognosis. Additionally, it aims to determine the vaccination and hospitalization rates of COVID-19 patients and assess the impact of vaccination on the clinical course of the disease.

Materials and Methods: The study included 80 patients over the age of 18 who were hospitalized with a diagnosis of COVID-19 at Meram State Hospital between September and December 2021 and were subsequently discharged. Patients' active complaints were recorded in the first and second months after discharge, and pulmonary function tests (PFT) were conducted. Data analysis was performed using SPSS 22.0.

Results: Of the participants, 52.5% (n=42) were female, with a mean age of 56.45 ± 1.4 years. While 16.3% of patients required intensive care, the average hospitalization duration was 12.48 ± 0.9 days. Among the participants, 23.8% (n=19) were smokers, and 66.3% (n=53) had at least one chronic disease. In the first month post-hospitalization, 91.3% reported fatigue, 86.3% reported exhaustion, 35.0% had sleep disturbances, 65.0% experienced shortness of breath, and 32.5% had muscle pain. A significant reduction was observed in complaints such as fatigue, exhaustion, sleep disturbances, and shortness of breath over a one-month follow-up period. FVC and FEV1 values were found to be higher in men than in women in both follow-up assessments. Vaccinated individuals had higher FVC and FEV1 values at the first follow-up compared to unvaccinated individuals. Smokers had lower FVC and FEV1 values in both assessments compared to non-smokers. There was a significant increase in FVC and FEV1 values between the two follow-ups, whereas FEV1/FVC remained stable.

Conclusion: This study indicates that a significant proportion of patients hospitalized due to COVID-19 continued to experience COVID-19-related symptoms for two months post-discharge. Among those who underwent pulmonary function assessments, individuals who had received at least two doses of the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine exhibited better respiratory capacities.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

COVID-19, post-acute COVID-19 syndrome, pulmonary function test, COVID-19 vaccines, Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine

INTRODUCTION

Coronaviruses (CoV) constitute a large family of viruses that can cause a spectrum of illnesses ranging from common cold-like self-limiting infections to severe conditions such as Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) (Corum, Grady, Wee, & Zimmer, 2020; Demir, 2020).

On March 11, 2020, the WHO declared COVID-19 a pandemic (Durduran, 2021). While some infected individuals required hospitalization, those in need of mechanical ventilation were treated in intensive care

units (ICUs) (Torres-Castro et al., 2021). COVID-19 primarily affects the lungs, causing widespread alveolar damage, hyaline membrane formation, and pulmonary consolidation (Mo et al., 2020). Studies conducted during the pandemic aimed to predict COVID-19 prognosis. Computed tomography (CT) imaging was used to classify disease severity through the Co-Rads system (Pekçevik & Belet, 2020). Pfizer-BioNTech vaccination commenced on April 12, 2021. The phase 3 clinical trials in Turkey reported an 83% efficacy rate for the Coronavac vaccine (Gürbüz, Aydın, & Çöl, 2021; Yavuz, 2020). Despite variations in efficacy across different variants, age groups, genders, and comorbidities, the BioNTech vaccine was found to be approximately 95% effective (GlatmanFreedman et al., 2021; Oliver, 2020). Vaccines play a crucial role in preventing infectious diseases and mitigating disease severity. Beyond their protective effect, vaccines are also noted for reducing the severity of infections (Sümer, 2011). Although the efficacy levels of COVID-19 vaccines differ, vaccination status has emerged as a key determinant of disease severity, with vaccinated individuals experiencing milder symptoms both during and after infection (Glatman-Freedman et al., 2021). This study aims to investigate whether vaccination, as a primary preventive measure against infectious diseases, contributes to disease prognosis. Additionally, it seeks to assess the hospitalization and vaccination rates of COVID-19 patients and evaluate the impact of vaccination on the clinical course of the disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Approval for this study was obtained from the Selçuk University Local Ethics Committee (decision number 2021/549, dated December 21, 2021). Permission was also granted by the Turkish Ministry of Health's COVID-19 Scientific Research Evaluation Commission on December 10, 2021. The Konya Provincial Health Directorate approved the study on January 5, 2022. The study included 140 patients who were diagnosed and treated for COVID-19 at Meram State Hospital between September and December 2021. The patients' sociodemographic characteristics (age, gender, chronic diseases) were recorded. Data regarding vaccination status, the type and number of vaccine doses received, ICU admissions, hospitalization duration, Co-Rads classification of lung involvement, hospital outcomes, and laboratory values at admission (ferritin, troponin, fibrinogen, D-dimer, CRP, LDH, AST, ALT, urea, creatinine, hemogram, and SpO₂ levels) were collected from hospital records. Patients who received at least two doses of Sinovac or one dose of Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine were considered vaccinated. Statistical analyses were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 for Windows at a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$. Descriptive statistics were used for single-group analyses, and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests were conducted to assess normality in continuous variables. Mann-Whitney U tests were used for comparisons of non-normally distributed data, while independent t-tests were applied for normally distributed variables. The study's power analysis was conducted using the Epi Info 1.4.3 software package. The minimum sample size required for a study population of 292 hospitalized patients over one month was determined to be 140, with 95% power and a 5% significance level.

RESULTS

The study included 140 participants aged 18 years and older, with a mean age of 62.91 ± 1.23 years. Of these, 52.1% (n=73) were male, and 22.9% required intensive care. The median hospital stay was 10 days (range: 4-53 days). Mortality was observed in 6.4% (n=9) of patients, while 93.6% (n=131) were discharged alive. Based on CT scan findings, Co-Rads classification showed 34.4% (n=48) as indeterminate, 42.1% (n=59) as high, and 23.5% (n=33) as very high. A total of 67.1% (n=94) of patients had at least one chronic disease. Vaccination coverage included at least two doses of Sinovac or one dose of Pfizer/BioNTech for 52.9% (n=74) of participants (Table 1).

Table 1
Sociodemographic Characteristics

		n	%
Gender	Female	67	47,9
	Male	73	52,1
Age	Mean±SE	62,91±1,23	
Intensive care	Yes	32	22,9
	No	108	77,1
Hospitalization Day	Mean±SE	10 (4-53)	
Outcome	Death	9	6,4
	Living	131	93,6
	Uncertain		
	High Very high		
Uptake by CT (Co-Rads)	Co-Rads-3	48	34,4
	Co-Rads-4	59	42,1
	Co-Rads-5	33	23,5
Chronic Disease	Yes	94	67,1
	No	46	32,9
Vaccination status	Yes	74	52,9
	No	66	47,1
Total		140	100

SE: standard error, min: minimum, max: maximum

Comparison of sociodemographic characteristics based on vaccination status indicated that unvaccinated individuals were more likely to be ≤62 years, require ICU admission, have higher mortality rates, and exhibit severe CT scan findings ($p=0.001$, $p=0.005$, $p=0.019$, $p=0.048$, and $p=0.018$, respectively) (Table 2).

Table 2
Evaluation of Sociodemographic Characteristics According to Vaccination Status

		Unvaccinated n (%)	Vaccinated n (%)	p [†]
Gender	Female	29 (43,9)	38 (51,4)	0,381
	Male	37 (56,1)	36 (48,6)	
Age	62 years and under	39 (59,1)	23 (31,1)	0,001
	62 years over	27 (40,9)	51 (68,9)	
Intensive care	Yes	44 (66,7)	64 (86,5)	0,005
	No	22 (33,3)	10 (13,5)	
Hospitalization Day	10 days and below	27 (40,9)	45 (60,8)	0,019
	10 days above	39 (59,1)	29 (39,2)	
Outcome	Death	7 (10,6)	2 (2,7)	0,048
	Living	59 (89,4)	72 (97,3)	
Uptake by CT (Co-Rads)	Uncertain	16 (24,2)	32 (43,2)	0,018
	High-Very high	50 (75,8)	42 (56,8)	
Chronic Disease	Yes	40 (60,6)	54 (73,0)	0,120
	No	26 (39,4)	20 (27,0)	
Toplam		140	100	

†: frequency, p value was found according to the chi-square test.

Furthermore, unvaccinated individuals exhibited lower age, urea, creatinine, leukocyte, and SpO₂ levels ($p<0.001$, $p=0.037$, $p=0.049$, $p=0.045$, and $p=0.009$, respectively). In contrast, unvaccinated patients had significantly longer hospital stays and higher ferritin, fibrinogen, LDH, AST, and ALT levels ($p=0.026$, $p=0.001$, $p=0.018$, $p<0.001$, $p<0.001$, and $p=0.016$, respectively) (Table 3).

Table 3

Evaluation of Age, Hospitalization Days and Blood Parameters According to Vaccination Status

	Unvaccinated Median (%25-%75)	Vaccinated Median (%25-%75)	P
Age Mean±SE	58,03±1,99	67,27±1,30	<0,001*
Hospitalization Day	12 (9-16)	10 (8-13)	0,026
Ferritin	286 (164-513)	174 (73-304)	0,001
Troponin	4,45 (2,5-11,0)	4,7 (2,5-10,5)	0,968
Fibrinogen Ortalama±SH	490,03±10,72	451,39±11,83	0,018*
D-Dimer	0,5 (0,3-0,8)	0,5 (0,3-0,8)	0,860
CRP	65,55 (35,1-118,0)	54,9 (24,8-118,0)	0,338
LDH	383 (297-464)	289,5 (241-371)	<0,001
AST	42 (31-55)	29,5 (22-41)	<0,001
ALT	24,0 (18-44)	19,5 (14-32)	0,016
Üre	30,5 (25-46)	38,5 (30-55)	0,037
Creatinine	0,89 (0,7-1,0)	0,96 (0,83-1,25)	0,049
Leukocyte	6,67 (4,8-9,8)	8,26 (5,86-11,03)	0,045
Hemoglobin	13,9 (13,2-14,7)	13,8 (12,3-14,9)	0,835
Lymphocyte	1,17 (0,7-1,6)	1,23 (0,8-1,6)	0,777
SPO ₂	90 (85-93)	92 (88-95)	0,009

p value was calculated by Mann Whitney U test, *: Independent Group T Test, SE: standard error, min: minimum, max: maximum

DISCUSSION

This study examined the clinical conditions of patients hospitalized due to COVID-19 and evaluated the effect of vaccination status on various clinical parameters. This study revealed that patients aged over 62, which was the average age, had higher vaccination rates, and vaccination rates increased with age. Older age is one of the most significant risk factors for COVID-19 (Barği, 2022). A study evaluating 2,968 hospitalized patients found that an increase in age by one year increased the probability of death by 5% (Nikpouraghdam et al., 2020). This higher vaccination rate in older populations may be due to the increased risk they face. The ICU admission rate for vaccinated patients was 13%, while the rate for unvaccinated patients was 33%. A study examining the protective efficacy of the CoronaVac vaccine found that it provided 83.5% protection against the disease (Tanriover et al., 2021). Another study on the Comirnaty vaccine found that it exhibited protective efficacy between 88% and 93% against various variants (Lopez Bernal et al., 2021). This study also demonstrated that vaccination reduced ICU admission rates. The median length of hospital stay for vaccinated patients was 10 days, while it was 12 days for unvaccinated patients. Numerous studies have shown that being unvaccinated increases the mortality rate and negatively affects prognosis (Göçmen et al., 2022; Göçmen et al., 2023). Similarly, this study found that vaccinated patients had a lower length of stay, mortality rate, and CT involvement rate, suggesting that vaccination had a positive effect on the clinical course of the disease. Various blood parameters are among the most important factors in predicting the severity of infectious diseases. For COVID-19, elevated levels of leukocytes, D-dimer, CRP, LDH, AST, ALT, creatinine, urea, ferritin, fibrinogen, troponin, and decreased levels of lymphocytes and SPO₂ at the time of admission have been used as prognostic markers in many studies (Arı, Kavuşak, Yanık, & Erten, 2023; Kalın & Solmaz, 2022; Keleş & Bozkurt, 2021). In this study, similar to other research, higher levels of ferritin, fibrinogen, LDH, AST, ALT, and lower SPO₂ levels were found to be more pronounced in unvaccinated patients, indicating poor prognosis.

CONCLUSION

Limitations of the Study: Due to the patients' diverse vaccination profiles, it was not possible to conduct a vaccine-specific analysis. Additionally, some of the high poor prognostic indicators in vaccinated patients may vary from one vaccine to another, and this could not be explained due to the diversity of vaccines used. Further studies with larger sample sizes and vaccine-specific analyses are needed.

Conclusion: Studies conducted to date have shown that, along with various clinical markers, vaccination status is one of the most important clinical indicators. This study specifically examined the effect of vaccination on the clinical course of COVID-19 and demonstrated its positive impact. Vaccination is the most significant method of protection against infectious diseases and also contributes positively to prognosis.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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